

TAXONOMIC CHARACTERISTICS OF GREEN ALGAE ON THE AZERBAIJANI COAST OF THE CASPIAN SEA

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The Caspian Sea is the largest isolated water basin in the world and its coastal zones differ with ecological conditions. Macrophyte algae are especially a key element in this ecosystem, provide food for primary producers and trophic nets. Green algae (*Chlorophyta*) are of a great value as the main primary producers—they significantly participate in the matter turnover, change and oxygen production and bioindication in an ecosystem of the sea [6, 157-158; 3, 50-53].

The Caspian is the largest leaf lake on Earth; it has coastal zones with various ecological subordination. Macrophytes algae are particularly relevant to this ecosystem and they represent an important food source for primary producers as well as different trophic chains. The Caspian green algae (*Chlorophyta*) are significant in the Caspian biota as a major group of freshwater primary producers, and they have a significant role in substance turnover, oxygen production, and bioindication in the ecosystem.

Thus, the investigation of the taxonomic structure and bioecological features of green algae (*Chlorophyta*) on the Azerbaijan coastal zone of the Caspian Sea is scientifically significant as a basis for assessing its ecosystems and biomonitoring. The purpose of this study is to investigate the diversity, habitat preference and anthropogenic influences on species of Chlorophyta from various coastal areas in the Caspian Sea.

Previously, according to research, in the 1970s, the list of macroalgae in the Caspian Sea included 63 species, including 29 green algae and mosses [14, p.45; 13, 200-205]. 76 species from 4 divisions, 6 classes, 15 orders, 21 families, and 42 genera were identified as a result of studies conducted in 1961–1963. Of these, 38 species and 1 subspecies were found in Baku Bay, and 12 species (8 green, 3 red, and 1 chara) were found on the southern Caspian Sea shores [12,190-200]. The dynamics of the proportions of the main algae groups depends on changes in sea level and salinity. In recent years, it can be seen that the proportions of algae groups have changed and the number of green algae species has increased. Green algae dominate in the north of the Caspian Sea. Green algae of the genera *Ulva* Linnaeus, *Cladophora* Kützing and *Ulothrix* Kützing form the core of the Caspian flora, which indicates a significant influence of river flow.

Macrophyte samples were collected from various substrate types (stony, sandy, muddy) at a depth of 0.5–5 m using a quadrat method on the Caspian coasts of Astara, Lankaran, Chabran, Siyazan, and the Absheron Peninsula in 2022–2024. The samples were studied using generally accepted methodology [11, p.182]. Species identification was carried out under a stereo microscope using regional floras and identification keys [13, 200-210; 11, p.5-230; 1, 10-45; 10, 325-340; 2, 10-70; 8, 36-45; 9, 85-90]. AlgaeBase [7], “California Academy” [5], websites were used to specify the names of algae species, referring to the latest nomenclature and their abbreviations were given according to Brummit and Powell [4, 10-210].

Studies conducted on the Azerbaijani coast of the Caspian Sea, the systematic composition and bioecological characteristics of macrophyte green algae (*Chlorophyta*) in different coastal zones were determined. In total, 21 species studied mainly belonged to four genera: *Cladophora*, *Chaetomorpha* Kützing, *Ulva* and *Rhizoclonium* Kützing. These genera belong to the *Chlorophyta Ulvophyceae* class, two main families - *Cladophoraceae* (*Cladophora*, *Chaetomorpha*, *Rhizoclonium*) and *Ulvaceae* (*Ulva*). When comparing systematic and species diversity across regions, 5 species were recorded on the northeastern coast (Siyazan–Shabran), where *Chaetomorpha linum*, *Cladophora glomerata*, *Rhizoclonium riparium*, *Ulva linza* and *Ulva compressa* were dominant. In the Lankaran zone, 9 species were identified in 2022, where several species of the *Cladophora* genus (*C. albida*,

C. fracta, *C. glomerata*, *C. sericea*, *C. ruchingeri*, *C. vagabunda*) were also present, as well as *Rhizoclonium riparium* and *Ulva species*.

As a result of research conducted on the Absheron Peninsula, 10 species were identified in 2023, where both the genera *Cladophora* and *Chaetomorpha* played a dominant role, and the species *Ulva compressa* and *U. prolifera* also had high abundance. In the southern zone, in the Lankaran-Astara areas, as a result of large-scale sampling conducted in 2023–2024, 16 species were identified, where all the main genera – *Cladophora*, *Chaetomorpha*, *Ulva* and *Rhizoclonium* – were represented. The abundance of both *Cladophora* and *Ulva* species in this region is striking and is associated with the influence of subtropical conditions. The results of the study show that species diversity and distribution of genera are closely related to the hydroecological conditions of the coastal zones and anthropogenic impacts. In the northeastern zone, due to climatic conditions and limited ecological conditions, only 5 species were observed, while in the central zone (Absheron), urbanization and industrial impact increased species abundance to some extent. In the southern zone, species richness was at its maximum level due to humid subtropical conditions and substrate diversity.

The analysis shows that the studied green algae species are able to adapt to different substrate types (stony, sandy, muddy). Most *Cladophora* and *Chaetomorpha* species are dominant in stony and rocky areas, while *Ulva* and *Rhizoclonium* species are dominant in sandy and muddy areas.

In terms of bioindicators, species such as *Ulva compressa*, *Cladophora glomerata* and *Rhizoclonium riparium* are considered indicators of pollution-tolerant, anthropogenically affected areas. On the contrary, species such as *Cladophora laetevirens* and *Ulva torta* characterize relatively clean and less affected areas.

Bioecologically, *Cladophora* and *Chaetomorpha* species predominated mainly in stony and rocky areas, while *Ulva species* were distributed in stony, sandy and mud-covered areas. Seasonal variation was observed in all zones, with more species being differentiated on the southern coasts, consistent with subtropical conditions. The dominant genera were *Cladophora* in all regions, while *Ulva species* were more widespread on the southern coasts.

As a result, the taxonomic composition and bioecological characteristics of macrophyte green algae on the Azerbaijani coast of the Caspian Sea differ across regions, and this difference can be associated with the hydroecological conditions of coastal zones, anthropogenic impacts, and climate. Thus, the *Chlorophyta* acts as an important bioindicator for assessing the state of ecosystems on the Caspian coast and for biomonitoring.

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